

Synthesis, characterization and electrochemical sensing property of quercetin using zinc tungstate nanorods

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Abstract : Zinc tungstate (ZnWO₄) nanoparticles were prepared by template free simple and cost effective precipitation method. The ZnWO₄ nanorods were synthesized by reacting 1 : 1 mole ratio of zinc acetate and sodium tungstate. The XRD pattern reveals that the synthesized ZnWO₄ has monoclinic structure. Further, the diffraction peaks were broadened due to the smaller size of the particle. The FT-IR analysis confirms the presence of Zn-O and W-O bonds in ZnWO₄ nanorods. The optical property of ZnWO₄ nanorods was carried out by DRS UV-Visible spectroscopy. The morphology of ZnWO₄ was investigated using SEM analysis and the electrochemical sensing behavior of ZnWO₄ nanorods towards (biomolecules) quercetin was investigated using cyclic voltammeter.

Keywords : ZnWO₄, electrochemical detection, quercetin, nanorods.

Introduction

MWO₄ type compounds where M is a divalent transition metal ion have attracted a lot scientific interest in recent times because of their many useful properties. In recent year metal tungstates were synthesized and used for various applications like photocatalyst¹, scintillator materials², sensor³ and so on. Zinc tungstate were synthesized using various methods like solid state synthesis⁴, solid state metathetic method⁵, sol-gel process⁶, aqueous solution phase growth⁷, polymerized complex matrix method⁸, molten salt preparation⁹, template method¹⁰, microwave assisted solvothermal process¹¹, self-propagating combustion analysis¹² and hydrothermal method¹³. In this work, we have synthesized the ZnWO₄ nanorods by simple and cost effective chemical precipitation method. Quercetin is an important component of flavonoids that are present in plants, fruits etc. People use quercetin as a medicine. Presence of high amount of quercetin may produce health harms to the human. Very high doses of quercetin can damage kidney. In the present work we have investigated the electrocatalytic property of as synthesized ZnWO₄ nanorods towards sensing of biomolecule quercetin.

Experimental

Reagent :

Zinc acetate and sodium tungstate were purchased from Qualigens and used as received. Quercetin was purchased from CDH, India. CTAB was purchased from Qualigens. Double distilled water was used throughout the experiment. All chemicals were used without further purification.

Synthesis of ZnWO₄ nanorods :

ZnWO₄ nanorods were prepared via direct precipitation reaction in aqueous media by addition of Zn²⁺ solution, in tungstate solution in the presence of cationic surfactant CTAB under vigorous stirring at room temperature. When the addition process was completed, the formed ZnWO₄ suspension was subjected to filtration process. Distilled water and ethanol was used for washing the obtained product and dried at 90 °C for 2 h. Finally the synthesized sample was annealed at 600 °C in order to improve the crystallinity of ZnWO₄.

Apparatus :

Synthesized ZnWO₄ was subjected to FTIR analysis using Shimadzu FTIR 8300 series instrument. XRD pattern of ZnWO₄ was recorded by a Rich Siefert 3000

diffractometer with Cu-K α_1 radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$). DRS UV-Vis absorption spectrum was recorded using Perkin-Elmer lambda 650 spectrophotometer. The morphology of synthesized ZnWO₄ was analyzed by HITACHI SU6600 Scanning Electron Microscopy coupled with EDAX. The electrochemical sensing experiments were conducted on a CHI 1103A electrochemical instrument using three electrode system in that working electrode was bare GCE and modified GCE, counter electrode was platinum wire, and reference electrode used was saturated calomel electrode (SCE).

Fabrication of ZnWO₄/GCE :

Suspension of ZnWO₄ was made by dispersing a 5 mg of ZnWO₄ in 10 mL of ethanol during 20 min of ultrasonic agitation. Before electrode modification, the working electrode was mechanically polished with alumina of different grades, it was rinsed, and then subjected to sonication for 2 min in distilled water. At last, the working electrode was coated with 10 μ L of the suspension by drop coating method and dried in air.

Results and discussion

Structural characterization :

In the XRD pattern of ZnWO₄ (Fig. 1), the diffraction peaks are well matched with standard diffraction of monoclinic ZnWO₄ (JCPDS 00-015-0774)¹⁵. From the observed data we concluded that the narrow diffraction peaks are

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of ZnWO₄ nanoparticles. Inset shows FTIR spectrum of ZnWO₄ nanoparticles.

produced and the corresponding cell parameter values are $a = 4.6986 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 5.7293 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 4.9367 \text{ \AA}$. Synthesized ZnWO₄ is in monoclinic phase having space group of p2/c. FTIR spectrum of ZnWO₄ is shown as inset in

Fig. 1. The spectrum shows a broad band at 3442 cm⁻¹ due to the presence of OH-stretching vibrations of both free and hydrogen-bonded hydroxyl groups^{16,17}. The absorption bands with their maxima at 833 and 873 cm⁻¹ are due to the stretching modes of W-O in WO₆ octahedral. The bands at 620 and 538 cm⁻¹ correspond to bridge oxygen atoms of the Zn-O-W with symmetrical vibrations. The band at 620 cm⁻¹ is due to the Zn-O stretching along the direction¹⁸, while the peak located at 471 cm⁻¹ is assigned to stretching vibration of Zn-O along the direction¹⁹.

Morphological analysis :

Fig. 2 shows the SEM image of ZnWO₄ prepared under above said experimental condition. As shown in this Figure, the morphology of ZnWO₄ obtained under experimental conditions is rod like morphology.

Fig. 2. SEM image of ZnWO₄.

Electrocatalytic property :

Fig. 3 shows the cyclic voltammograms of 0.1 mM quercetin at bare GCE and ZnWO₄ modified GCE

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram of bare GCE and ZnWO₄/GCE.

(ZnWO₄/GCE) in 0.1 M KCl at the scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹. A broad oxidation peak at 0.18 V was observed for bare GCE. Whereas an oxidation peak at +0.15 V with enhanced anodic current response (3.96 μA) was observed for ZnWO₄/GCE. From the cyclic voltammograms, it is clear that the ZnWO₄/GCE shows oxidation potential for quercetin which was shifted to less positive direction with higher current response than the bare GCE, indicating that the ZnWO₄ modified GCE has strong electrocatalytic ability towards quercetin which may be due to the large available surface area¹⁶, surface hydroxyl group¹⁷ and variable oxidation state of the W ions in ZnWO₄¹⁸.

Conclusion

Zinc tungstate nanorods were prepared by simple precipitation method. The ZnWO₄ nanorods were analyzed by XRD, FTIR and the rod-like morphology of ZnWO₄ was confirmed by SEM. The synthesized nanorods were subjected to modify the GCE to investigate the electrocatalytic activity towards biomolecules like quercetin. The results exhibit that the ZnWO₄ nanorods will be a great potential in the field of biomolecules electrochemical sensor.

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